

ON THE STUDY OF PHRASEOLOGISMS IN MODERN ENGLISH

Pazilova Nasibaxon Muhammadqosimovna

Andijan state foreign languages institute, docent

Iskhakova Aliya Ildarovna

1st year master degree student of linguistic department at Andijan

State Institute of Foreign Languages

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Annotation. This article is devoted to the problems of phraseological unit and its historical development. It also discusses the characteristic features of phraseological unit in Modern English.

Key words: phraseologism, equivalent, synonymy, phrase, phonetic and semantic connection.

Phraseology is a separate branch of linguistics, which studies fixed combinations and expressions based on figurative meaning. "Phraseology". the Greek term "pharsis" means phrase, expression "logos" means doctrine, and only stable compounds based on figurative meaning are included in its scope of research. The vocabulary of the language consists not only of other words, but also of free word combinations. Free word combinations serve as a means of understanding phrases with other words. Stable word combinations show words connected in a subordinate relationship [1].

Phraseological combinations consist of two or more words, it can express one concept and be equivalent to one word, usually it has a one-word synonymous equivalent, syntactically forming a part of a sentence. According to their structure, phraseological combinations show great variety. Semantic connections between the composition of phraseological units can be different, the word included in such units retains its independence of meaning at a high or low level.

By the 60s and 80s of the 20th century, interest in the field of phraseology grew rapidly in foreign literature, including English literature. Until that time, there was no separate work dedicated to phraseology in Western and American linguistics. In general, the term "phraseology" was first used by Charles Bally in his work "Precis de stylistique". The first researcher in the field of phraseology is undoubtedly the Swiss-French linguist Charles Balli. In his works "Essay on Stylistics" (1905) and "French Stylistics" (1909), he included special chapters on word combinations and phraseologisms.

English and Americans can be proud of having rich dictionaries, but apart from the short applications noted in works in general linguistics, there were still the most important theoretical problems that have not been solved, not only not

Among them, William L. Graff, he really gave a linguistic analysis of the difference between phraseological idioms and stylistically freely connected words.

Graff used the terms "expression" or "units of expression" in his works and defined it as a unit and a model unit consisting of words that cannot be replaced without changing the meaning of the unit and its parts. His approach combined contextual analyzes and diachronic observations. The components of one expression are used so many times in phonetic and semantic connections with another that they are even separated as a complex unit. Graff was very interested in how to change that unit from a free construction to a simple word. Graff began to prove his views with the following relations:

"He left him a fortune",

"He left him at home"

"He left him in the lurch" compared the sentences and emphasized that the relation of the verb and the complement in the first two sentences is not connected. If we say "He gave him a fortune" or "He saw at home" or if we use it in many sentences in other large texts, the meanings expressed by the words "fortune" and "at home" are almost identical which would not have been changed. In the third sentence, unlike the others, it is significant that the meaning is subordinate to the word "lurch" and is connected with the verb "leave" which cannot be replaced by any other verb. It is clear from Graff's applications that all parts of "to leave in the lurch" are understood to be interrelated.

It has been more than 75 years since this theory was written. Graff says that the currently used word "breakfast" is also extracted from the stable combination "to break fast", that is, when "break" is combined with the word "fast", which means "to refrain from eating", only this word is a verb with a specific meaning. Therefore, it was appropriate to say "And knight and squire had broken their fast" (W. Scott).

In fact, it was not a word, but a word combination is clearly indicated by the syntactic relationship of the noun and the declension relationship of the verb. Graff briefly touched upon this problem in his General Linguistics Guide. Another important, unsolved problem was the problem of classification. Detailed groupings are given in the English Phrasebook by L.P. Smith and W. Ballarn. At that time, the authors themselves did not confirm that these groupings were accepted as classification of phraseological combinations. They simply collected stable compounds, explained them, illuminated some of their interesting

aspects, i.e. alliteration, rhyme, contrast, etc., and interpreted the expressiveness clarifying mechanisms. They were also interested in the etymology and origin of phraseological combinations in the English language and arranged them according to the words derived from marine life, agriculture, hunting, sports and others. The language's wealth of resources makes it an invaluable practical guide to everyday vocabulary for those interested in teaching and learning English. [2].

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